

Paper 10

**INFORMATION ASSURANCE: THE WAY TO
INTRODUCE IN UG EDUCATION IN INDIA—A
POLICY FRAMEWORK**

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Abstract

Information Assurance (IA) is an important and emerging concepts related to the information security. Information Assurance (IA) is also required for the managing and implementing information security related policies. There are two types of security; firstly traditional security and another one is computational security. Traditional security is about the manual documents and content related security whereas; computational security is deals with various components based security viz. Network Security, Web Security, Database Technology, Multimedia Technology etc. Information Security is very close with the Information Assurance (IA), as it is also deals with Manual and Computational areas; though it is additionally deals with the policies, regulation and guidelines of security. Many universities internationally offered degrees and academic programs on Information Assurance (IA) and allied fields viz. Information Assurance and Security, IT and Information Assurance, Computer and Information Assurance, IT Security and Assurance etc. The degrees are offered in different levels viz. Bachelors Degree, Masters Degree, PG Diploma, PG Certificate, Doctoral and Post Doctoral level; there are different universities. In India, a very few universities have started security related degrees and most of these are offering traditional nomenclatures. There are potentialities to offer the degrees at UG levels with little initiatives and policies. This paper is talks about such potentiates and situation in detail.

Keywords: Information Assurance, UG Education, Indian Higher Education, Research Degrees, IT Security

1. Introduction :

Information Assurance is an emerging field of Computing and Information Technology responsible for the privacy and security management in the institutions and organizations [4], [24]. Information Assurance is responsible for different affairs leading to designing, development, as well as management computational systems and additionally manual

information systems. It is a broader field than Information Security and emerged in recent past. Moreover, the field is interdisciplinary in nature. The need of cyber security including data privacy different universities are providing academic programs and courses on these areas leading to Cryptography, Computer Security, Information Technology Security, Information Security etc. Information Assurance is a broad field that incorporates all the subjects related to the security and privacy both in technological and managerial way. Information Assurance is an emerging concept in government and administration as well [1], [3], [8]. The leading, innovative and emerging universities worldwide is offering different program on Information Assurance and its subfields. In India huge number of educational institutes offers IT and Computer related education in different levels. And few of such universities started specialization and subfield in Information Technology [4], [5], [14].

2. Objective and Agenda

The paper is conceptual in nature and theoretical as well, it deals with formulation of following agenda and objective—

- To learn about the basics of Information Assurance including its smaller and broader area.
- To find out the nature and characteristics of Information Assurance.
- To learn about the function and need of Information Assurance education program at present day context.
- To learn about the availability of the programs on Information Assurance and allied discipline in international educational institutes.
- To find out the way to introduce Information Assurance and allied fields at Under Graduate level in Indian universities.
- To learn about the challenges and issues in introducing Information Assurance subject in Indian universities.

3. Information Assurance: Overview

Information assurance is dedicated to different form of information and data management; hence it is responsible for healthy digital and physical content management. Electronic device privacy and security is also the concern in Information Assurance field [6], [7], [11]. National Institute of Standards and Technology defined Information Assurance dealing *any measures that protect and defend information and information systems by ensuring their availability, integrity, authentication, confidentiality, and non-repudiation. These measures include providing for restoration of information systems by incorporating protection, detection, and reaction capabilities.*

Information Assurance is also deals policy and process of its different sub field and it may include IT Security, Information Security etc. Technological system fulfillment is the ultimate goal of Information Assurance and apart from these Management principle are also important

aspects of this field [9], [10], [15]. There are different affairs to be performed by the Information Assurance professionals—

- Corporate Governance using Information Assurance principles
- Planning, formulation of the regulation and standard of Information Assurance
- Auditing of Information Security and its products
- Disaster recovery related to information system and infrastructure

Information Assurance is composed with different sub fields viz. Information Security (and this is composed with IT Security), Information Technology Security (It composed with different part viz. Database Security, Web Security, Network Security, Software Security etc), Computer Security (focused on Cryptography and Encryption) etc [12], [13], [18].

4. Information Assurance and Allied Education

Information Assurance is today not a concept rather it is an emerging research area and academic program in many international universities [10], [16], [22]. However different universities used different nomenclatures of this field which include but not limited to—

- Information Assurance
- Cyber Security and Information Assurance
- Information Assurance & Security
- Information Assurance & Information Systems Management etc

However the curricula differ from university to university and focused on different areas viz. Communication Technology, IT Risk Management, Advanced Network Security Design, Web System Security, Cybercrime Management & Response etc. STRAYER University, US offers the degree of MS Information Assurance with Cyber Security as a specialization and comes with following

- Information Systems for Decision Making
- Theories of Security Management
- Communication Technology
- Advanced Computer Architecture
- IT Risk Management
- Advanced Network Security Design
- Web Application Security
- Cybercrime Techniques & Response
- IT Audit & Control
- Security Access and Control Strategies

Similarly, the field Information Assurance is also comes with UG Degree in few universities and offers both technological and managerial affairs of the security the in course contents.

5. India and UG Education in Computing and Information Field

India is a largest education system in the universe composed with different types of educational institutes. The UG education is normally offered by the Colleges and few universities. India holds 40000+ HEIs (Higher Educational Institutes). The UG Degrees in Computing and allied field available with following degrees—

- Bachelor of Science
- Bachelor of Technology
- Bachelor of Engineering
- BCA (Bachelor of Computer Applications)
- Bachelor of Vocation

Whereas these degrees are offered with different computing related subjects and specializations viz.—

- Computer Science
- Computer Application
- Computer Science and Engineering/ Technology
- Information Science
- Information Technology
- Information Systems
- Information Science and Engineering etc

6. Way to Introduce IA in Indian Academics at UG

It is worthy to note that as per the study adopted, following international universities offers Information Assurance and allied subjects—

- BS-IT (Information Assurance and Cyber Security), offered by the Capella University, United State/ 180 Credit
- BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance, offered by the City University of Seattle, United State/180 Credit
- BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance, offered by the University of Michigan-Dearborn, United State/ 106 Credit

The syllabus also varies, instead of only core subjects of Information Assurance, the universities offers wide range of courses based on requirement. Here in Table: 1 depicted curricula of City University of Seattle, United State with 180 Credit.

Table: 1- Information Assurance program at UG level, City of University of Seattle

Programs and University	Curriculum Focus on the Security
<p>BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance,</p> <p>Offered by the City University of Seattle, United State.</p> <p>Having 180 Credit</p>	<p>Basics for the Degree</p> <p>Fundamentals of Accounting Introduction to Web Design Any Two Research Methods & Practice Justice and Ethics Criminal Procedural Law Principle of Micro Economics</p> <p>Governance, Risk Management, and Compliance Core (45 Credits)</p> <p>Cybercrime, Technology, and Social Change (5) Cyber and Surveillance Law and Governance (5) Investigation of Cyber Crime (5) Applied Criminology and Crime Prevention (5) Enterprise Risk Management (5) Homeland Security and Espionage (5) Policy and Audits (5) IT Compliance (5) Investigation of Business Crimes (5) Or Risk Assessment and Prevention (5)</p> <p>Cybersecurity Technology Core (40 Credits)</p> <p>Network Communications Basics (5) Network Security (5) Data Management Communications and Networking (5) Internet Technologies (5) Information Systems (5) Information Security (5) Tools and Techniques (5) Computer Science I: C++ (5) Or</p>

	<p>Programming with Python (5)</p> <p>Required Electives (10 Credits) Any Two</p> <p>Legal Issues in the Workplace Operations Management (5) Fundamentals of Criminology (5) Investigation of Business Crimes* (5) Organizational and White-Collar Crime (5) Communicating Crisis, Emergency, and Social Change (5) Systems Analysis and Design (5)</p> <p>Capstone (5 Credits) Bureaupathology (5)</p>
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It is important to note that most of the universities offers the field Information Assurance with focus on technologies and managerial aspects leading to security and privacy [17], [19], [20]. The mentioned syllabus includes Governance, Risk Management, and Compliance Core Courses for 45 Credit and Cyber Security Technology Core for 40 Credit.

Hence as far as India is concerned, the field may be started as a full-fledged degree nomenclature and some of such degrees are mentioned in Table: 2; though the field may also offer as a Major or Specialization in Information Assurance and allied nomenclature. In India, Computing related Bachelor Degrees are available in different forms and thus different major based degrees are proposed in the field and these are depicted in Table: 3 and 4.

Table: 2 Possible UG Degrees in Information Assurance in Indian Context

Information Assurance Full fledged Degrees
BSc/BTech/BE in Information Assurance BSc/BTech/BE in Cyber Security and Information Assurance BSc/BTech/BE in Information Assurance & Security BSc/BTech/BE in Information Assurance & Information Systems Management etc

Table: 3 Possible specialized UG Degrees in Information Assurance in Indian Context

Information Assurance in BSc Programs (Major)
BSc- Information Technology (Information Assurance) BSc- Information Science (Information Assurance)

BSc- Computer Science (Information Assurance)
 BSc- Computer Applications (Information Assurance)

It is worthy to note that these programs may also be available in other merged nomenclature and these include— Information Assurance, Cyber Security and Information Assurance, Information Assurance & Security, Information Assurance & Information Systems Management etc as a major.

Table: 4 Depicted possible specialized UG Degrees in Computer Applications in Indian Context

Information Assurance in BCA Programs (Major)
BCA in Information Assurance BCA in Cyber Security and Information Assurance BCA in Information Assurance & Security BCA in Information Assurance & Information Systems Management etc

This way, the field Information Assurance may be offered in different form in existing programs as well as full-fledged

7. Issues and Challenges

- The field Information Assurance is emerging and interdisciplinary in nature and thus the skill providers needs knowledge in both technological and managerial areas.
- Different allied departments or possible collaborative departments may be tied-up for offering the interdisciplinary areas if possible or available viz. law, management, public administration etc.
- Industrial tie-ups is required to built to offer the Information Assurance programs in skill based context.
- Universities and educational institutions are not interested to change the traditional systems, and there is a less awareness about the field in the academic institutes, faculties and students.
- The emerging sub fields of Information Assurance such as Cloud Security, Big Data and Mobile Security is an emerging issues.

8. Conclusions with Suggestion

Information Assurance and Privacy is the need of hour, today almost all kind of organizations and institutions are using technological systems for their operation data management [14], [21], [23]. Additionally the organizations are also doing the traditional data management and thus knowledge organization tools may be used. The emerging Cloud Security, Big Data and Mobile Security should be incorporated in the curricula, moreover the industrial skill based vendor certification curricula may also required to incorporate in the syllabus for more suitable product

development. India is a largest educational systems and variety of Bachelors degrees are offered in the Computing field and thus with proper initiative and strategy easily Information Assurance may be started.

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